

Prevalence Rate of Hepatitis C Among Patients Undergoing Ocular Surgeries at A Tertiary Care Hospital of Western UP

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Abstract

Objectives: To study the prevalence rate of Hepatitis C among patients undergoing ocular surgeries between the age of 18-80 years at Muzaffarnagar Medical College.

Methods: This hospital-based observational study was conducted at the Department of Ophthalmology, Muzaffarnagar Medical College and Hospital, covering a population in age group of 18-80 years undergoing ocular surgeries. Data collection spanned 18 months, with a sample size of 500. Patients undergoing ocular surgeries were tested for Hepatitis C by Rapid chromatography immunoassay for qualitative detection of antibodies and positive results were confirmed by ELISA.

Results: The study found a prevalence of 5.6% of Hepatitis C in patients undergoing ocular surgeries in a tertiary care hospital of western UP. Majority of patients were in the age group of 61-70 years. It was observed that the patients who were tested positive for Hepatitis C were mainly from the rural background and most of them belonged to lower socio-economic status.

Conclusion: A 5.6% prevalence rate of Hepatitis C in our study underscores the importance of targeted screening, particularly among high-risk groups identified by age, gender, residence, and socio-economic status before performing any ocular surgery. The findings emphasized the necessity for focused public health interventions to address the disparities and enhance management and prevention strategies for Hepatitis C among patients undergoing ocular surgeries. Also, by knowing the status of infectivity of patients, we as operating surgeons, can ensure proper precautions while operating.

Keywords: Hepatitis C, Ocular surgeries, Cataract, Rapid Chromatography Immunoassay.

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Introduction

Hepatitis is defined as swelling and inflammation of the liver which may lead to cirrhosis or cancer on progression [1]. Sometimes people contract hepatitis with limited or no symptoms but often it leads to jaundice, anorexia (poor appetite) and diarrhoea. Hepatitis is caused by a wide variety of causatives like alcohol, poison and autoimmunity but most cases of hepatitis are due to infection by viruses [1].

Hepatitis C (HCV) is a type of infective viral Hepatitis that leads to irritation, inflammation and swelling of the liver, capable of causing acute and chronic form of hepatitis [2]. According to WHO

estimates, HCV prevalence is 3% of world population with 170 million cases. Almost 50% of all cases become chronic carriers and are at risk of liver cirrhosis and liver cancer [3].

HCV, however, can only be contracted through blood-to-blood contact [4]. The transmission risk of these diseases is more among patients receiving blood transfusions or drug abusers using injections [5]. The risk of HCV can be avoided by use of disposable syringes, screened blood transfusion, avoidance of sexual abuse and use of proper antiseptic measures in hospitals, clinics and operation theatres [6]

There is lack of routine serological screening prior to surgery which is one of the factors responsible for increased disease transmission. The major risk factors include re-use of contaminated syringes, surgical instruments, and improperly screened blood products [6].

The aim of this study was to estimate the prevalence of Hepatitis C among patients undergoing ocular surgery at Muzaffarnagar Medical College. This study included the patients who underwent ocular surgeries like cataract, pterygium, glaucoma, and lid surgeries.

Methods

It was an observational study done in the department of Ophthalmology, Muzaffarnagar Medical college, UP. All patients admitted for ocular surgery were screened for Hepatitis C infection. Written informed consent was taken from all the patients who agreed to take part in our study. Data was collected regarding patient's clinical history and co-morbidities. The findings were recorded in a structured compilation sheet and analysed through application of statistical tools of analysis. All patients of 18 years of age and above that presented themselves with ocular pathologies and scheduled for ocular surgery at the department of Ophthalmology were included in the study. Patients below 18 years and those who had systemic pathological condition or patients who had received anti-HCV treatment were excluded from the study. Rapid chromatography immunoassay for qualitative detection of antibodies for Hepatitis C was the screening technique used in the study. Positive results were then confirmed by ELISA (Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay).

Results

The study titled "Hepatitis C among Patients Undergoing Ocular Surgeries at a Tertiary Hospital of Western UP" was conducted as a hospital-based observational study. It took place in the Department of Ophthalmology at Muzaffarnagar Medical College, Muzaffarnagar, Uttar Pradesh. The sample size comprised 500 patients who had undergone ocular surgery in the Ophthalmology Department at Muzaffarnagar Medical College and Hospital.

The study's analysis of HCVAg status among patients with Hepatitis C who underwent ocular surgeries revealed that 5.6% of the patients were HCVAg positive, while the remaining 94.4% were HCVAg negative as shown in Figure 1. The p-value of less than 0.001 indicated that the difference in the frequency of HCVAg positivity among the patients was statistically significant.

In our study, the age distribution among Hepatitis C patients who underwent ocular surgeries revealed

notable trends. The majority of patients fell within the age group of 61-70 years comprising 45% of the total sample, with 2.4% tested positive for Hepatitis C. The 51-60 years age group also showed a high prevalence, representing 21.4% of the total sample, with 1.6% positivity. In the 41-50 years age group, 21.6% of total patients were observed, with a 0.6% positivity rate. Lower frequencies were found in the 31-40 and 18-30 age groups, representing 5.4% and 3.6% of the total patients respectively and positivity rates of 0.4% and 0.2%. The 71-80 age group, although representing only 3% of the total sample, had a 0.4% positivity rate as shown in Figure 2. The overall positivity rate for Hepatitis C was 5.6% across all age groups. The p-value of 0.002 indicated that the differences in Hepatitis C positivity rates across the various age groups were statistically significant.

Our study evaluated Hepatitis C detection methods among patients who underwent ocular surgeries and compared the effectiveness of Rapid Chromatography Immunoassay and ELISA. For Rapid test, 5.6% of the patients were tested positive while 94.4% tested negative out of a total of 500 cases. ELISA showed a positivity rate of 100% and a negativity rate of 0% among the 28 cases that were tested positive by Rapid Chromatography Immunoassay. These findings highlighted the distribution of positive and negative cases detected by each method as shown in Figure 3.

Discussion

Hepatitis C is a single stranded enveloped RNA virus, belongs to family Flaviviridae, transmitted primarily via blood, body surface secretions and by piercing through percutaneous veins and mucosal surfaces. Hepatitis C virus has an incubation period of 14 to 180 days with an average of 45 days. It can occur in both acute and chronic forms leading to cirrhosis [7], hepatic encephalopathy, coma and death. Worldwide, an estimated 130-150 million people (2-3%) are living with Hepatitis C infection with highest prevalence in developing countries.

The study titled "Hepatitis C Among Patients Undergoing Ocular Surgeries in a Tertiary care Hospital of Western UP" was conducted as a hospital-based observational study. It took place in the Department of Ophthalmology at Muzaffarnagar Medical College, Muzaffarnagar, Uttar Pradesh. The sample size comprised 500 patients who had undergone ocular surgery in the Ophthalmology Department at Muzaffarnagar Medical College and Hospital. In our study we found that majority of cases of Hepatitis C who underwent ocular surgeries were between 61-70 years of age, accounting for 42% of the total sample. This was followed by the 51-60 years age group with 24%. In our study we also found that a greater proportion of patients were from rural areas,

comprising 60.2% of the total sample. In contrast, 39.8% of the patients were from urban areas.

In our study we analysed HCVAg status among patients undergoing ocular surgeries which revealed that 5.6% of the patients were HCVAg positive, while the remaining 94.4% were HCVAg negative. The p-value of less than 0.001 indicated that the difference in the frequency of HCVAg positivity among the patients was statistically significant.

In our study we compared the effectiveness of Rapid Chromatography Immunoassay and ELISA among patients undergoing ocular surgeries. For Rapid test, 5.6% of the patients tested positive while 94.4% tested negative, out of a total of 500 cases. Similarly, ELISA showed a positivity rate of 100% and a negativity rate of 0% among the 28 cases that were tested positive by Rapid test. These findings highlight the distribution of positive and negative cases detected by each method. All the patients who were tested positive for HCV then underwent quantitative assessment by immunochromatography and were given subsequent treatment by the Department of Medicine at Muzaffarnagar Medical College. In a study by Jatoi et. Al, they used rapid chromatography immunoassay for Hepatitis C antigen detection in 1128 patients enrolled for eye surgery who were unaware of the infection [8].

Conclusion

The study 'Hepatitis C Among Patients Undergoing Ocular Surgeries in a Tertiary care Hospital of Western UP' conducted at Muzaffarnagar Medical College revealed significant epidemiological insight. The highest prevalence of Hepatitis C was observed in the 61-70 years age group, with males showing a slightly higher frequency of infection compared to females. Rural residents and individuals from lower socio-economic classes were more affected, highlighting socio-demographic disparities in the prevalence of Hepatitis C. Marital status also played a role, with married individuals showing a higher infection rate. Observing the HCV prevalence rate of 5.6% in

western U.P., our study underscores the importance of targeted screening, particularly among high-risk groups identified by age, gender, residence, and socioeconomic status before performing any ocular surgery. The detection methods, ELISA and Rapid immunochromatography, both demonstrated their efficacy in identifying Hepatitis C cases, reinforcing the need for comprehensive diagnostic approaches in clinical settings. These findings emphasize the necessity for focused public health interventions to address the disparities and enhance the management and prevention strategies for Hepatitis C among patients undergoing ocular surgeries. Also, by acknowledging the status of infectivity of patient, we as operating surgeons can ensure proper precautions while operating.

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